

FAIR data principles	FAIR metrics for comparison Bootstrap FAIR MIs (Maturity Indicators; Wilkinson et al., 2019, S. 3) doi.org/10.1038/s41597-019-0184-5 https://github.com/FAIRmetrics/Metrics	RDA FAIR data maturity model Working Group WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG Outputs and Recommendations doi.org/10.15497/rda00050 doi.org/10.5334/dsp/2020-041 https://www.r4-alliance.org/system/files/FAIR%20Data%20Maturity%20Model_%20Specification%20and%20Guidelines_v1.00.pdf	RDA (Vertiefung) Priority	FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics doi.org/10.5291/zenodo.5461229 https://www.fair4ai.eu/fair4ai-data-object-assessment-metrics-request/comments	FAIRsFAIR (Vertiefung) More concrete implemented in FAIR assessment tool F-UJI (e.g. https://www.fujit.net/view/172)	EOSC FAIR data metric (not existing) // European Open Science Cloud doi.org/10.2777/70791 https://rop.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ced147c9-532c-11eb-b59f-01aa75ed71a1		
F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier	FM-F1-B - persistent	F1: RDA-F1-01M - Metadata is identified by a persistent identifier	●●● Essential	--	--	--		
		F1: RDA-F1-01D - Data is identified by a persistent identifier	●●● Essential	FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier	FsF-F1-01D-1: Identifier is resolvable and follows a defined unique identifier syntax (IRI, URL) FsF-F1-01D-2: Identifier is not resolvable but follows an	EOSC-F1-01D - Data is identified by a persistent identifier		
	FM-F1A - unique	F1: RDA-F1-02M - Metadata is identified by a globally unique identifier	●●● Essential	--	--	--	--	
		F1: RDA-F1-02D - Data is identified by a globally unique identifier	●●● Essential	FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier	FsF-F1-02D-1: Identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax FsF-F1-02D-2: Persistent identifier is resolvable	EOSC-F1-02D - Data is identified by a global unique identifier		
F2. Data are described with rich metadata	FM-F2 - rich metadata	F2: RDA-F2-01M - Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery	●●● Essential	FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability	FsF-F2-01M-1: Metadata has been made available via common web methods FsF-F2-01M-2: Core data citation metadata is available FsF-F2-01M-3: Core descriptive metadata is available	Concise examples given	EOSC-F2-01M - Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery	
F3. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	FM-F4 - indexed	F4: RDA-F4-01M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed	●●● Essential	Enabling of harvesting and indexing	FsF-F4-01M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines	FsF-F4-01M-1: Metadata is given in a way major search engines can ingest it for their catalogues (JSON-LD, Dublin Core, RDFa) FsF-F4-01M-2: Metadata is registered in major research data registries (DataCite)	Enabling of harvesting and indexing	EOSC-F4-01M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed
		-- for data			-- for data			-- for data
F4. Metadata specify the data identifier	FM-F3 - Identifier of the data	F3: RDA-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier for the data	●●● Essential		FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describe	FsF-F3-01M-1: Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type) FsF-F3-01M-2: Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content		EOSC-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier for the data
A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol	--	A1: RDA-A1-01M - Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data	●● Important	--	--	--	EOSC-A1-01M - Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data	
		A1: RDA-A1-02M - Metadata can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)	●●● Essential	--	--	EOSC-T-A1-03M - Metadata can be accessed manually (i.e., with human intervention)		
		A1: RDA-A1-02D - Data can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)	●●● Essential	--	--	EOSC-T-A1-03D - Data can be accessed manually (i.e., with human intervention)		
		A1: RDA-A1-03M - Metadata identifier resolves to a metadata record	●●● Essential	additional aspect	--	--	--	
		A1: RDA-A1-03D - Data identifier resolves to a digital object	●●● Essential	additional aspect	--	--	EOSC-A1-02D - Data identifier resolves to a digital object	
		A1: RDA-A1-04M - Metadata is accessed through standardised protocol	●●● Essential	--	FsF-A1-02M - Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol	FsF-A1-02M-1: Landing page link is based on standardized web communication protocols	EOSC-A1-03M - Metadata is accessed through standardized protocol	
		A1: RDA-A1-04D - Data is accessible through standardised protocol	●●● Essential	--	FsF-A1-03D - Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol	FsF-A1-03D-1: Metadata includes a resolvable link to data based on standardized web communication protocols	EOSC-A1-03M - Data is accessed through standardized protocol	
		A1: RDA-A1-05D - Data can be accessed automatically (i.e. by a computer program)	●● Important	--	--	--	EOSC-A1-04D - Data can be accessed automatically (i.e., by a computer program)	
		A1.1. the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	FM - A1.1 - open, free and universally implementable	A1.1: RDA-A1.1-01M - Metadata is accessible through a free access protocol	●●● Essential	--	--	--
				A1.1: RDA-A1.1-01D - Data is accessible through a free access protocol	●● Important	--	--	--
A1.2. the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, which necessary	FM - A1.2 - authentication and authorization	A1.2: RDA-A1.2-01D - Data is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorisation	● Useful	--	--	--		
				FsF-A1-01M - Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data	FsF-A1-01M-1: Information about access restrictions or rights can be identified in metadata FsF-A1-01M-2: Data access information is machine readable FsF-A1-01M-3: Data access information is indicated by (not machine readable) standard terms	Focus on metadata, not the protocol		
A2 metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	FM - A2 - even when the data are no longer available	A2: RDA-A2-01M - Metadata is guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available	●●● Essential	--	FsF-A2-01M - Metadata remains available, even if the data is no longer available	--	EOSC-A2-01M - Metadata is guaranteed to remain available, after data is no longer available	
I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation	FM - I1 - language for knowledge representation	I1: RDA-I1-01M - Metadata uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format	●● Important	--	FsF-I1-02M - Metadata uses semantic resources	FsF-I1-02M-1: Vocabulary namespace URIs can be identified in metadata FsF-I1-02M-2: Namespaces of known semantic resources can be identified in metadata	EOSC-T-I1-01M - Metadata uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format	
		I1: RDA-I1-01D - Data uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format	●● Important	--	--	--	EOSC-T-I1-01D - Data uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format	
		I1: RDA-I1-02M - Metadata uses machine-understandable knowledge representation	●● Important	--	FsF-I1-01M - Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language	FsF-I1-01M-2: Parsable, graph data (RDF, JSON-LD) is accessible through content negotiation, typed links or sparql endpoint	EOSC-I1-01M - Metadata uses machine-understandable knowledge representation	
		I1: RDA-I1-02D - Data uses machine-understandable knowledge representation	●● Important	--	--	--	EOSC-I1-01D - Data uses machine-understandable knowledge representation	
I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	FM - I2 - vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	I2: RDA-I2-01M - Metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies	●● Important	--	--	EOSC-I2-01M - Metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies		
		I2: RDA-I2-01D - Data uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies	● Useful	--	--	--		
I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	FM - I3 - qualified references	I3: RDA-I3-01D - Data includes references to other data	● Useful	--	--	--	--	
		I3: RDA-I3-02D - Data includes qualified references to other data	● Useful	--	--	--	--	
		I3: RDA-I3-01M - Metadata includes references to other metadata	●● Important	--	FsF-I3-01M - Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities	FsF-I3-01M-1: Related resources are explicitly mentioned in metadata FsF-I3-01M-2: Related resources are indicated by machine readable links or identifier	--	
		I3: RDA-I3-02M - Metadata includes references to other data	● Useful	--	--	--	--	

		I3: RDA-I3-03M - Metadata includes qualified references to other metadata	●● Important						
		I3: RDA-I3-04M - Metadata include qualified references to other data	● Useful						
R1. (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	--	R1: RDA-R1-01M - Plurality of accurate and relevant attributes are provided to allow reuse	●●● Essential		FsF-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data	FsF-R1-01MD-1: Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata (Resource type e.g. dataset / datacontent given in metadata) FsF-R1-01MD-2: Verifiable data descriptors (file info, measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata (filesize / measurement info given in metadata) FsF-R1-01MD-3: Data content matches file type and size specified in metadata FsF-R1-01MD-4: Data content matches measured variables or observation types specified in metadata	Content of data appears less specific and comprehensive than "attributes"	EOISC-R1-01M - Plurality of accurate and relevant attributes are provided to allow reuse	
R	R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	FM - R1.1 - accessible data usage license	R1.1: RDA-R1.1-01M - Metadata includes information about the licence under which the data can be reused	●●● Essential	FsF-R1.1-01M - Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused	FsF-R1.1-01M-1: Licence information is given in an appropriate metadata element FsF-R1.1-01M-2: Recognized licence is valid and registered		EOISC-T-R1.1-01M - Metadata includes information about the licence under which the data can be reused	
		--	R1.1: RDA-R1.1-02M - Metadata refers to a standard reuse licence	●● Important	--			EOISC-T-R1.1-02M - Metadata refers to a standard reuse licence	
	--	R1.1: RDA-R1.1-03M - Metadata refers to a machine-understandable reuse licence	●● Important	--				EOISC-R1.1-01M - Metadata refers to a machine-understandable reuse licence	
	R1.2. (meta)data are associated with their provenance	FM - R1.2 - provenance	R1.2: RDA-R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information according to community-specific standards	●● Important	Extension of provenance format to community	FsF-R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation	FsF-R1.2-01M-1: Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information and can be mapped to PROV FsF-R1.2-01M-2: Metadata contains provenance information using formal provenance ontologies (PROV-O)		EOISC-R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information according to community-specific standards
			R1.2: RDA-R1.2-02M - Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language	● Useful	Extension of provenance format to community				--
	R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	FM-R1.3 - community standards	R1.3: RDA-R1.3-01M - Metadata complies with a community standard	●●● Essential		FsF-R1.3-01M - Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data	FsF-R1.3-01M-1: Community specific metadata standard is detected using namespaces or schemas found in provided metadata or metadata services outputs FsF-R1.3-01M-2: Community specific metadata standard is listed in the re3data record of the responsible repository FsF-R1.3-01M-3: Multidisciplinary but community endorsed metadata (RDA Metadata Standards Catalog) standard is listed in the re3data record or detected by namespace		EOISC-T-R1.3-01M - Metadata complies with a community standard
--			R1.3: RDA-R1.3-01D - Data complies with a community standard	●●● Essential		FsF-R1.3-02D - Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community	FsF-R1.3-02D-1: The format of a data file given in the metadata is listed in the long term file formats, open file formats or scientific file formats controlled list	Data refers only to file format	EOISC-T-R1.3-01M - Data complies with a community standard
--		R1.3: RDA-R1.3-02M - Metadata is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard	●●● Essential		--			EOISC-R1.3-01M - Metadata is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard	
--		R1.3: RDA-R1.3-02D - Data is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard	●● Important		--			--	